

Solvent hydrogen bonding and structural effects on reaction of 2-chloro-3,5-dinitropyridine with *para*-substituted anilines in dimethylformamide/acetonitrile mixtures

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Abstract : Substitution reactions of some *para*-substituted anilines with 2-chloro-3,5-dinitropyridine were carried out conductometrically in dimethylformamide/acetonitrile mixtures. The rate data correlate poorly with macroscopic solvent parameters while excellently with Kamlet-Taft's solvatochromic parameters ($100R^2 = 97\%$). The computed percentage contributions of these parameters ($P_\alpha = 65\%$, $P_\beta = 34\%$, $P_{\pi^*} = 1\%$) suggests that the specific solute-solvent-solvent interactions influences the reactivity to a greater extent. These solvent effects on the reactivity were also explained on the basis of electronic spectra and cyclic voltammetric techniques.

Keywords : Solvent effect, aniline, Hammett equation, hydrogen bonding, kinetics.

Introduction

The study of influence of solvent on the reactions of anilines in non-aqueous and aquo-organic solvent mixtures has revealed the important role of non-specific and specific solvent effects on reactivity¹⁻⁶. It has been shown that the reactivity is influenced by the preferential solvation⁷ of the reactants and/or transition state through non-specific and specific solvent-solvent-solute interactions. Examination of the literature revealed that the effects of structure on S_N2 reactions have largely been reported⁸⁻²². However, only very few attempts have been made to study on the effect of solvent on such reactions in a more systematic manner²³⁻²⁹. Hence in this article, the reaction of few *para*-substituted anilines with 2-chloro-3,5-dinitropyridine in dimethylformamide (DMF)/acetonitrile (AcN) (both polar, aprotic, hydrogen bond acceptor, PAHBA) mixtures of varying compositions has been reported. To study the effect of solvent and structure on the reactivity 2-chloro-3,5-dinitropyridine (CDNP) is chosen as the substrate, in the present investigation, as the kinetics of its reaction with aniline in neat organic solvents is known³⁰.

Experimental

All the chemicals (Aldrich or Merck, India) used were of analytical grade. The solvents DMF and AcN were of spectroscopic grade and were used as received. The solid anilines were used as such and the liquid anilines were used after vacuum distillation. The kinetic studies, FT-IR studies and data analysis were carried out as described earlier³¹. The product analysis was also done as reported earlier³¹ by employing GC-MS technique and the results reveal that the reaction product was 2-phenylamino-3,5-dinitropyridine (m/z 260; $M^{+\bullet}$) and its fragmentation with m/z ratio 184 and 92 respectively.

Results and discussion

The nucleophilic substitution reaction of parent aniline and a few *para*-(Et, Me, OMe, F, Cl and NO₂) substituted anilines with CDNP was studied conductometrically in the presence of varying excess (aniline) over the substrate to ensure pseudo-first order kinetics. The selection of the mole fractions for the reaction was based on the fact that the solvatochromic parameters employed in the

present study for correlation analysis are available in the literature³⁰. Based on the kinetic results and the product analysis the following reaction (Scheme 1) has been proposed for the reaction of anilines with CDNP which involves a transition states (I). The formation of such a type of transition state was well established in the S_N2 reactions of aromatic amines with various substrates⁸⁻¹².

Fig. 1 shows the solution FT-IR spectrum of the reaction mixture at different time intervals. The doublet around $2930-3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponds to asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of the two N-H bonds of the aromatic primary amine³². It is evident from the figure that with lapse of time the intensity of the peak decreases which confirms the participation of the amine group in the reaction.

Thermodynamic parameters and the isokinetic relationship : The activation parameters for the reaction of

Scheme 1

Fig. 1. FT-IR spectra of the reaction mixture in acetonitrile with increase in time.

all the substituted anilines with CDNP at 0.5 mole fraction of DMF were calculated from k_A at 303, 313 and 323 K and are collected in Table 1. The operation of

Table 1. Effect of temperature on the rate of reaction of anilines with 2-chloro-3,5-dinitropyridine in 0.5 mole fraction of DMF and activation parameters for the reaction

Substituents in aniline	Rate constants $10^3 k_A$ (s^{-1})			ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger (303 K)
	303 K	313 K	323 K			
None	0.58	2.91	3.00	66.30	-925	94.3
<i>p</i> -Et	2.03	2.35	2.65	84.61	-275	91.7
<i>p</i> -Me	1.21	2.10	2.66	26.69	-228	96.1
<i>p</i> -OMe	1.92	2.34	2.75	12.56	-261	91.8
<i>p</i> -F	1.85	1.89	2.03	13.15	-299	91.9
<i>p</i> -Cl	2.68	4.75	5.28	25.64	-215	90.8
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	1.60	1.96	2.39	13.95	-258	92.3

ΔH^\ddagger in kJ mol^{-1} ; ΔS^\ddagger in $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$; ΔG^\ddagger in kJ mol^{-1} .
 [Aniline] = 0.1 M, [CDNP] = 0.001 M.

isokinetic relationship is tested according to eq. (1) as suggested by Exner³³.

$$\log k \text{ (at } T_2) = a + b \log k \text{ (at } T_1) \quad (1)$$

In the present study linear plots imply the validity of isokinetic relationship ($r = 0.98$, $sd = 0.03$, isokinetic temperature = 492 ± 18 K). The operation of isokinetic relationship reveals that all the substituted anilines examined follow a common mechanism. Negative entropy of activation indicates a greater degree of ordering in the transition state than in the initial state, due to an increase in solvation during the activation process.

Likewise, the activation parameters were also calculated for aniline in different mole fractions of AcN (Table 2). The result reveals that increase in mole fraction of DMF in the medium increased the rate of the reaction. The existence of a linear relationship ($r = 0.95$, $sd = 0.10$, isokinetic temperature = 330 ± 17 K between $\log k_A$ at 313 K and $\log k_A$ at 303 K) indicated that a single mechanism is operating in all the solvent mixtures under scan.

Structure-reactivity correlation : The effect of substituents on the rate was studied with seven *para*-substituted anilines. The results reveal that in a given mole fraction the rate constants vary with the nature of the substrate. The rate data failed to conform to either the

Table 2. Rate constants ($10^3 k_A$, s^{-1}) and activation parameters for the reaction of aniline with 2-chloro-3,5-dinitropyridine in various mole fractions of DMF in AcN

Mole fraction of DMF	Rate constants $10^3 k_2$ (s^{-1})			ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger (303 K)
	303 K	313 K	323 K			
0	0.12	0.58	1.26	93.5	-169	98.6
0.1	0.23	0.89	1.59	78.0	-628	97.0
0.2	0.25	1.65	2.00	84.1	-405	96.4
0.3	0.35	1.90	2.56	81.0	-485	95.7
0.4	0.37	2.02	2.92	83.3	-404	95.6
0.5	0.58	2.91	3.00	66.3	-925	94.3
0.6	1.37	3.09	3.68	38.7	-177	92.5
0.7	1.89	3.91	4.01	28.8	-207	91.6
0.8	2.02	4.56	4.98	35.1	-186	91.5
0.9	2.89	5.07	5.69	25.6	-214	90.6
1.0	3.15	5.91	6.12	25.0	-215	90.4

ΔH^\ddagger in kJ mol^{-1} ; ΔS^\ddagger in $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$; ΔG^\ddagger in kJ mol^{-1} .
 [Aniline] = 0.1 M, [CDNP] = 0.001 M.

usual Hammett equation or its modified ones; plots of $\log k_2$ versus substituent constants are non-linear (not shown).

Solvent-reactivity correlation : The title reaction has been studied in eleven different mole fractions of DMF in AcN. The second order rate constants increased with an increase in mole fraction of DMF in the mixture. The correlation of rate data with Reichard's³⁴ polarity parameters E_T (30) is just satisfactory with an explained variance of less than 93%. Such a correlation may be due to the fact that bulk solvent properties like E_T (30) will poorly describe the microenvironment around the reacting species, which governs the stability of the transition state and hence the rate of the reaction.

Therefore, in order to obtain a deeper insight into the various solute-solvent interactions, which influence reactivity, we have tried to adopt the solvatochromic comparison method developed by Kamlet and Taft³⁵. The kinetic data were correlated with the Kamlet-Taft's solvatochromic parameters α , β and π^* . The rates of the reaction of aniline with CDNP studied showed an excellent correlation with the solvent with an explained variance of 97%. The statistical results and weighted percentage contributions of the solvatochromic parameters is shown in the following equation. Such an excellent correlation indicates the existence of specific solute-solvent interactions in the reactions.

$$\log k_A = -0.075(\pm 3.21) - 0.075(\pm 3.21)\pi^* + 3.29(\pm 0.66)\alpha - 1.71(\pm 0.74)\beta$$

$$(N = 11, R^2 = 0.97, sd = 0.11, P_\alpha = 65\%, P_\beta = 34\%, P_{\pi^*} = 1\%) \quad (2)$$

The UV-Visible absorption spectra of the reactants in the solvent mixture and the solvatochromism exhibited by them adequately support the conclusions derived above. It is evident from the results that, the peak position of UV absorption (λ_{\max}) shows little dependence on the solvent (<1%). In contrast, the absorption intensity (ϵ_{\max}) exhibits a significant increase (>25%) from 2740 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹ in AcN to 3705 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹ in DMF. Thus, ϵ_{\max} is likely to be affected by hydrogen bonding³⁶.

This observation can qualitatively be explained as : since DMF is a non-hydrogen-bonding solvent while AcN exhibits a potential ability to donate a hydrogen atom towards the formation of an H-bond, the latter can interact with aniline through HBD property but not the former one. This point of observation has also been explained quantitatively through correlation analysis. The intermolecular solute-solvent interactions through H-bonding were examined by correlating ϵ_{\max} of aniline against the Kamlet-Taft's solvatochromic parameters α , β and π^* (eq. 3), as this equation comprises both the HBD and HBA terms in it.

The result of the correlation is represented as :

$$\log \epsilon_{\max} = 3.15(\pm 0.17) + 0.44(\pm 0.21)\pi^* - 0.14(\pm 0.04)\alpha - 0.05(\pm 0.01)\beta$$

$$(N = 11, R^2 = 0.96, sd = 0.01, P_\alpha = 22\%, P_\beta = 8\%, P_{\pi^*} = 70\%) \quad (3)$$

It can be seen from the results that the absorption intensity is influenced by both specific and non-specific solute-solvent interactions as indicated by the percentage contributions of α , β and π^* parameters. Among specific interactions, the contribution of α term is found to be dominant and the negative sign of coefficient of this term suggests that the absorption intensity would decrease with increase in HBD property of the medium. The contribution of HBA property (P_β) towards the solvation of aniline by the solvent mixture is less significant. Thus increase in the mole fraction of DMF in the mixture progressively decreases the solvation around the NH₂ moiety of aniline molecule and consequently increases the absorption in-

tensity. Hence the observed increase in rate of the reaction between aniline and CDNP with increase in the mole fraction of DMF might be due to the desolvation of the NH₂ moiety to a relatively greater extent. Such a solvation of aniline by can through HBD property around the reaction centre would make the approach of the reaction partner comparatively difficult and consequently retard the rate of the overall reaction.

The above mentioned fact was further supported by cyclic voltammetric studies of aniline in the given solvent mixtures. The cyclic voltammogram of aniline with varying mole fraction of DMF is depicted in Fig. 2. The anodic peak at ~1.3 V corresponds to the electro-oxidation of aniline. This oxidation potential shifts towards the

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammogram for the oxidation of aniline (1×10^{-3} M) in different mole fractions of DMF at a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹ (The direction of the arrow indicates the shift in oxidation potential with increase in mole fraction of DMF).

less positive side with an increase in the mole fraction of DMF in the mixture suggesting that the removal of electron from NH₂ moiety (oxidation) becomes increasingly easier. A plot of oxidation potentials, E_{p_a} versus mole fraction of DMF is linear ($r = 0.96$, $sd = 0.009$) with negative slope. The decrease in the oxidation potential of aniline with a decrease in non-HBD property of the medium was observed earlier by us in the study of electro-oxidation of anilines in water/2-methylpropan-2-ol³⁷ mixture. As the pair of electrons on the NH₂ moiety is well

surrounded by the HBD solvent molecules, its participation in the formation of the transition state (I) will be difficult and consequently the rate of the reaction will be decelerated.

Conclusion :

The solution FT-IR studies show that, the substitution reaction involves a transition state in which the amine group is participating. The correlation of the reaction rates with solvent via Kamlet-Taft equation indicates the existence of specific solute-solvent interactions in the present study. Further hydrogen bonding donor (HBD) ability of the solvent plays a major role in governing the reactivity and the rate of the reaction was found to increase with decrease in HBD property of the medium. The formation of a transition state as depicted in (I) is well supported by the solvent and structural effects.

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